

THE USE AND REPRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY OF LANDSCAPE FLOWERING LIANAS IN LANDSCAPING

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Abstract. For the purpose of landscaping around the world, an assortment of local and tropical plants is used. The countries of the European Union are one of the areas where vertical landscaping in the United States is very important. In our state, as in foreign countries, the overheating of the walls and roof parts of multi-storey buildings as a result of hot temper in the summer months is a problematic phenomenon. For this reason, there is a need for vertical landscaping of buildings and constructions, besedkas, phytodevor, Alleya from decaying, flowering lianas.

Keywords. Manzarali gullovchi liana, ko`kalamzorlashtirish, ko`paytirish texnologiyasi.

INTRODUCTION

Tashkent region is located in the subtropical climate of the northern hemisphere and is sharply continental. The distribution of the heat goes back to the seasons. From May to September are considered warm months, and from June to July there is a high temperature. The coldest months are December, January and February. Early arrivals and evening frosts in this area are also observed. If in the spring the first decadal of March are colder, then in the autumn there is a frost in the second decadence of November. Absolute maximum temperature is equal to +45⁰C, absolute minimum-30⁰S. The first frosts fall on 10 October. But in some

years the last frosts are observed in the second December of April, the first frosts are also observed on 25 September. The table below shows the distribution of heat.

Table 1

Average, maximum and minimum temperatures of the air, °C (average multi-year data of the Tashkent meteorological station)

Temperature display-small	Months												Average annual
	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	
Average	-0,6	1,9	7,9	14,7	20,1	24,9	27,0	25,0	19,6	12,8	6,6	1,9	13,5
Maximum	22	26	33	35	42	44	45	43	40	38	31	24	35,3
Minimum	-28	-26	-20	-6	0	4	8	6	0	-11	-22	-30	-10,4

Starting from 1962, there were established plant – growing farms in seven cities of the Republic-Andijan, Angren, Almalyk, Bukhara, Samarkand, Fergana and Urgench. The land area of these farms was 592 hectares. On the basis of the Research Institute of Forestry, the Republican Center for landscape gardening and forestry was established in 2005 [5] in order to establish landscaping on a scientific basis.

In the study of a single landscape tree or shrub species, forest scientists and production activists are studied in a case based on their literature sources and experiences. In particular, it is worthwhile to get acquainted with the history of the work and literature on the direction of vertical landscaping of Tekoma (Naychagul) – campus Radicans(Seem), Chinese glycine – Wisteria Sinensis (Sums), Japanese Jimolosti – Lonicera Japonica (Thumb) lianas [3].

In our research on my Master's dissertation work on the scientific justification of vegetative reproduction of landscape flowering lianas in vertical landscaping, which is currently the most popular direction of landscaping, we will

study the history of this subject, many theoretical and practical literature, laws and decisions devoted to the prospects of development in the present day.

Basically, the book covers various compositional techniques of vertical landscaping, in detail gives an expanded assortment of plants with decorative and agrobiological properties, describes about 50 compositions from ornamental lianas with species of plants, other plant groups (flowering plants, annual ornamental lianas). Each composition emphasizes the individual artistic value of plant species and combinations individually, the period of its greatest decorativeness is indicated, and recommendations for its use in the design of various objects are given. The book is widely summarized the latest achievements of Ukrainian scientific research, local and foreign practice in the field of vertical landscaping, and is developed on the basis of the best examples of landscaping with plants of residential buildings, public buildings and other regions of Ukraine, Russia, Latvia, Estonia. It is about vertical landscaping of cities.

The book, published in the Uzbek language, provides very brief information about the vertical field of landscaping.

Since the problem of landscaping is directly related to the world of plants and trees, several sources related to dendrology have also been worked on, and for the problem being handled, relevant materials have also been relied on in dendrology.

Vertical landscaping and landscaping work is a factor that has a huge positive impact on the environmental environment, and from this point of view, I got acquainted with several textbooks and manuals devoted to the problems of our Republic and World Ecology.

Bannikov A.G., Vekulin A.A., Rustamov L.K. In his book "Osnovi ekologii i oxrana okrujayushey sredi", he mentioned the positive effects of vertical landscaping on ecology.

The book describes the impact of both landscaped areas on ecology.

In the book "Fundamentals of Ecology and the use of nature", it is presented about the need for the nature of greenery.

In this literature, in turn, the Master's thesis is reflected in the theoretical paragraphs. The process of analyzing the literature studied in order to make specific conclusions on the problem and solution of the problem that the master poured on the topic of dissertation has shown that the field of landscaping has been significantly studied both from an ecological and Urban point of view.

Issues of development of Park composition techniques and theory of landscape art, volumetric-spatial organization of the territory and development of objects of landscaping are covered. The methodology for the formation of plantations, reconstruction and restoration of historical gardens was described. Advanced domestic and foreign experiments on landscaping were summarized. For students of the direction of landscaping of residential areas of the population mentioned about lianas.

Belyaeva E. in "Modnie tendensiiv ozelenenii" book of have described plant and flower species of modern species for vertical landscaping.

The history of vertical gardening, methods and common prints of modern cities, which are increasingly being implemented using the latest designs and systems of Russian and foreign manufacturers, will be considered. The application of new technologies in the creation of green walls was based. A comparison and

analysis of two fundamentally different technologies was carried out. Issues of aesthetic, environmental and rationalization character will be discussed.

In this book, the necessary tips are shown in depth, but due to the climate of the Republic there are no specific and necessary recommendations on vertical landscaping, as well as selected plants. The analyzed literature on the topic of vertical landscaping has shown that it is necessary to conduct scientific and practical research on vertical landscaping, to choose the most suitable plants for the ecomohiti of cities and to create the necessary compositions from them should be studied as an urgent problem.

The article is devoted to vertical landscaping - one of the most popular types of modern landscape design. Particular attention is paid to the types of vertical landscaping and the conditions of its use. The advantages and disadvantages of this type of landscaping are determined. The impact of vertical landscaping on human life and ecology will be considered.

In modern vertical landscaping, a wide range of plant species is used, which are located" vertically " or are used for objects located at an altitude above the ground: vertical landscaping of roofs and walls of public and residential buildings, garages and closed parking lots, terraces of buildings, balconies and logics, etc. It includes all the above types of vertical landscaping. Here is a brief overview of the innovations of the world, emphasizing the achievements in the landscaping of roofs and walls of Buildings.

Vertical landscaping is one of the effective landscape design methods. It is made with the help of lianas, trees and shrubs, allows you to give the maximum green color mass, creates the illusion of a green environment, hides part of the walls from the eyes, decorates the facades of buildings, emphasizing their beauty, creating

a unique and unforgettable appearance. This contributes to the creation of a special atmosphere in parks, parks and indoor gardens.

This Casablanca, Morocco, anfa population living in the quarter of 5 skyscrapers vertical landscaping has passed on. The article provides such an idea of vertical landscaping: at all stages of its development, a person is closely connected with the world around him. But the rapid development of the industry has been the subject of people's interference in nature since the emergence of society, the boundaries of the industry and now it becomes a global threat to people. The most common and, importantly, chemical pollution of the environment. The accumulation of carbon dioxide gas in the atmosphere continues. Taking into account the environmental problems of cities, it is worth noting that transport and industrial enterprises have been built excessively in the residential areas, causing great damage to the urban environment, it is noted that in large cities it is important to plant greenery in the city on account of the presence of 10 times more aerosols and 25 times more gases in

This article discusses the global problem of atmospheric pollution. The solution to this problem is to multiply the areas of greenery. Vertical landscaping on the walls of the building in the conditions of a limited area for the placement of green spaces, which appeared as a result of the implementation of vertical landscaping in the skyscrapers, is the most urgent solution.

1-picture. Multi-year average, highest and lowest indicators of air temperature, °C

Table 2

Average, maximum and minimum temperatures of the soil surface, 0C

Temperature display-small	Months												Average annual
	January												
Average	-2	4	8	17	24	31	34	31	23	13	5	0.3	16.0
Maximum	25	35	48	58	64	71	71	70	64	53	38	27	52.0
Minimum	-35	-24	-30	-5	-2	5	9	3	-4	-8	-32	-31	-13.7

2.2-rasm. Tuproq yuzasining o`rtacha, maksimum va minimum haroratlari, °C

Perennial average, lowest and highest indicators of the soil surface. The maximum temperature in Absalyut is also recorded in July: in 2015, 45 0C heat was registered. The average lowest temperature on the soil surface was also observed in January. In 2015, the temperature of -4 0C was recorded.

The absolute minimum temperature is -24 0C in Yanvar. The highest temperature of the soil surface was also in July, this month the soil surface was heated to 70 0C.

Table 3

Relative humidity of air, %

Months												Average annual
January												
72	70	66	61	55	43	40	44	46	57	67	74	58

Dry air is considered to be very humid air, if the relative humidity of the air is below 30%, then 71-80%, if the average humidity is higher than 80%. In Uzbekistan, the humidity of the air varies throughout the year, which is also indicated by many years of data on the tables.

For example, at the beginning of summer, the amount of precipitation sharply decreases, at this time the air humidity is much lower than in the meyor, dry and hot weather occurs.

In June-July, the lowest air humidity was recorded (32-37). Relative humidity of air closely correlates with the season of collection of precipitation can be seen from the table: precipitation is a lot of precipitation fevar-in March, air humidity also had high indicators. Precipitation is also not evenly distributed throughout the year, it corresponds mainly to the winter spring season.

In general, the annual amount of precipitation in the Tashkent Oasis was 411 mm, based on many years of data. 60-70% of this amount of precipitation falls on winter-spring snow-rains. In summer, it also rains partially (2-10 mm).

3-picture. Relative humidity of air and change in the amount of precipitation by months

4-picture. Distribution of wind speed by months

The average wind speed in the Tashkent Oasis is 1.6–2.1 m/sec. Strong winds are observed in March-April-May. If we analyze the reversal indicators of the wind, we can see that the winds blow mainly from the North East Tamon. In the southern and south-eastern directions, winds were observed less often.

Soil conditions. Dark-tinged Boz soils in the Tashkent Oasis rise to 1200-1300 m in the mountainous regions. In these soils, the amount of humus is 1.92-2.95%, with an increase in depth, the amount of cumin decreases. In the plain part

of the Oasis, typical burlap soils are scattered, in which the plowing layer consists of layers that are clearly separated. The element that forms the soil is lyoss.

The groundwater is located at a depth of 5-6 m. For complete harakterization of soil conditions, special soil shurfi at a depth of 2 m is dug and soil layers are studied.

1. A plow 1 layer 0-35 CM –the arable top of the Earth is a horizontal, moist, orange-gray structure sac-shaped, on average many plant root residues and worm or triples. Skip to the next row Mar in a row.

2. A2 35-36 CM-the horizon under the arable part of the Earth, dark gray in its novelty, limestone residues with a diameter of 1-2 cm, concentrated in the process of processing into unstructured soil, perennial grass roots threeraydi.

3. B1 60505 CM –three of limestone and stones sometimes 1-6 CM in diameter, soaked, without structure, densifying, hungry-Gray in freshness. Perennial grass roots threeraydi.

4. B2 105-148 CM-in its freshness, light gray, wet breeze is porous, heavy, without structure, the roots of the grassy Arrow are encountered in the ahyon.

5. C 148-200 CM - light brown, with a lot of moisture heavy suede, structured, unstructured perennial herbaceous roots less than threeraydi. The soil actively boils without acid, which indicates the presence of carbonate in its composition.

According to the mechanical composition, the powder-clay is of the same type. According to the mechanical composition, the most light C is the 148-200cm horizon.

The granulometric analysis of the soil showed that in the soil layer of 2 meters, particles smaller than 0.01% constitute 43-53%.

Particles of size 1-0.25 mm increase with increasing depth of soil: ash at 0.54% in the layer of 0-35 CM threeraydi in the amount of 2.07% in the horizon of C 148-200 CM.

The highest amount of humus in the soil is threeraydi in layers. Its quantity as it deepens. The most abundant indicator of nitrogen is also recorded in the upper horizon.

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